

Feasibility of Using Current Transformers as Sensors for Non-invasive Fuel Monitoring

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Acronyms

AC	Alternating Current
CT	Current Transformer
PuMA	Pump Monitoring Apparatus
V_{RMS}	root mean square Volts
V	Volts
Vdc	direct current Volts
ms	milliseconds
MR	magnetoresistor
Hz	Hertz
kΩ	kiloohm
mL	milliliter
MHz	megaHertz
DC	direct current
AC	alternating current
PPE	personal protective equipment

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1 Introduction

Alaska's cold climate results in high energy use and costs for space heating. Improving the energy efficiency of a building can help reduce both of these variables. However, one must be able to measure the energy used for space heating to assess the efficacy of energy efficiency measures. Many households in Alaska use vented fuel oil heaters to heat their homes because they are fuel efficient and relatively inexpensive compared to other heating appliances. However, the flow of fuel oil used by these appliances is very low and therefore difficult to measure. The Alaska Center for Energy and Power developed a fuel metering technology called the Pump Monitoring Apparatus (PuMA) for use with vented fuel oil heaters. The PuMA, with a $\pm 7\%$ variance from measured fuel consumption in lab testing, is more accurate than other run-time fuel monitoring systems which produce errors ranging from 13% to 27% [1] [2].

The PuMA is non-invasive, meaning that it does not require the fuel line to be broken into to measure fuel use. Instead, it uses a magnetoresistive (MR) sensor placed against the heater's solenoid-driven positive displacement fuel pump to detect the operational state of the heater (off, low, medium, or high) and the number of cycles completed by the piston within the fuel pump. The amount of fuel displaced per pump cycle differs for the low, medium, and high combustion settings. Multiplying the number of piston cycles by the volume of fuel displaced per pump cycle allows one to calculate the fuel used by the appliance.

The MR sensor must be properly positioned to sense the magnetic field produced by the solenoid for the PuMA to collect data. If the MR sensor is displaced from that position, the PuMA cannot collect data on fuel pump activity, and thus, fuel consumption. The PuMA has been deployed in three field studies in Alaska to measure heating fuel oil consumption, and MR sensor displacement has been an issue, resulting in a loss of data collection. Replacing the MR sensor with a current transformer (CT) to sense pump cycles would improve the field performance of the PuMA by making it more robust to movement. As long as the CT remains around the electrical line to the solenoid, the PuMA will continue to collect data. This report describes the procedure and results of tests on four current transformers to determine their suitability for replacing the MR sensor currently employed by the PuMA.

2 Theory

2.1 Current Transformers

Current transformers (CTs) are a type of transformer; they modify incoming electrical energy to increase or decrease voltage by using a wire wrapped around a core [3]. Current sense transformers are generally used to monitor power flowing through an alternating current (AC) line by reducing the voltage. This is done by having a high turns ratio around the core of the transformer. The turns ratio is defined by the ratio between the number of times the input line (primary) is wrapped divided by the number of times the output line (secondary) is wrapped around the core in the transformer. The primary value is usually 1, unless it is deliberately wrapped around the transformer more times. The secondary turns value is often in the hundreds or even thousands. Ideal current transformers are linearly proportional to the current they are measuring.

In order to prevent arcing or a short circuit, a resistor to limit current must be used on the outputs of the transformer. This resistor is called the "burden resistor" or "burden" and is in series with the internal resistance. A higher burden equates to a higher voltage output, and a lower burden results in a lower voltage output. Sensing transformers are often rated by the V_{RMS} of their output, which limits the size of the burden. The minimization of sine wave distortion must also be considered when designing burden sizes if preserving the waveform is desired.

There are three types of CTs. The first type is invasive and requires a wired connection from the input lines to the transformer. The other two are non-invasive types, split- and solid-core, where the input line goes through the core of the transformer. Split-core transformers are designed with a hinge, which opens and can be placed around the input line. Solid-core transformers must have the line fed through the aperture. Figure 1 shows the basic operation of a non-invasive solid-core transformer I is the input current, B is the magnetic field, A is the ammeter measuring the transformer current, and N is the turns ratio.

Figure 1. A diagram of a partially coiled non-invasive solid-core transformer. [4]

2.2 Vented Fuel Oil Heaters

There are several ways that fuel is transferred from the fuel tank to the combustion chamber depending on what technology is used for heating. For the most commonly encountered vented heaters in Alaska, a sump and positive displacement solenoid pump are used as follows:

1. From the holding tank, fuel is piped to where the heater is installed.
2. A fuel sump assembly controls the fuel intake via a float or other mechanism. The fuel accumulates in the sump.
3. A fuel pump transfers fuel from the sump to the combustion chamber.
4. Fuel is then combusted and the flow rate of the fuel is controlled for each setting.

To drive the solenoid pump, a square wave of several milliseconds pulse width and an amplitude of roughly 150 volts direct current (Vdc) is sent to the pump, with the frequency dictating the flow rate [1]. Higher frequencies

Figure 2. A general parts diagram of a Toyotomi Laser 531/532. Note the fuel sump and pump on the lower right. [5]

correspond to higher flow rates. Volume per cycle of the solenoid pump is on the order of 1×10^{-5} liters per cycle or 0.01 mL per cycle [1]. Flow rates are around half a liter per hour [5]. See Figure 2.

2.3 The Intersection

The majority of current sense transformers on the market are meant for measuring sine waves, from tens of hertz (Hz) to MHz frequencies and currents from hundreds of milliamps (mA) to thousands of amps. Vented fuel oil heaters, on the other hand, use a pulsed square wave with a constant length of 4ms and magnitude of around 150 V and frequencies ranging from 0 Hz (off) to around 20 Hz [1]. Because of the discrepancy between the waves, frequencies and currents these transformers are designed to measure and those produced by vented fuel oil heaters, testing must be conducted to determine whether current transformers are a viable option for replacing the MR sensor on the PuMA for non-invasive fuel monitoring.

3 Experimental Setup

3.1 Materials

3.1.1 Current Transformers

To ensure that the PuMA remains relatively affordable, the current sensor selected should not cost much more than the MR sensor it will be replacing. The current MR sensor design costs around \$4. While low current transformers exist with relatively low turns ratios, they can be prohibitively expensive and/or difficult to procure due to low stocks. Four non-invasive current transformers were selected based on their low cost, and somewhat appropriate design based on their current ratings and turns ratios, and ease of installation. See Table 1.

Manufacturer	Model	Type	Turns Ratio	Cost	Reference
CR Magnetics	CR84110-1000	Solid-core	1000	\$12	[6]
CR Magnetics	CR3110-3000	Split-core	3100	\$18	[7]
Kemet	CT-06-50	Solid-core	500	discont.	[8]
Talema Group	AZ-0500	Solid-core	500	\$9	[9]

Table 1. CTs' Details

3.1.2 Damping Fluid

For the fuel pump to operate and respond properly, it must be circulating a fluid. Operating it without fluid risks damaging the pump by breaking the piston or by overheating. However, petroleum fuel products are irritants, toxic, and difficult to handle safely indoors. Therefore, a non-aqueous alternative was used based on having a similar viscosity to fuel oil. PSF-2cSt Pure Silicone Fluid was chosen since it is widely used in products such as deodorants and cosmetics and is known to be nontoxic [10].

3.2 Setup

3.2.1 Electrical

Figure 3. The physical layout of the parts and their respective electric connections.

Figure 3 shows the parts and electrical connections of the test setup, which is based on a setup used previously for testing heater fuel pumps and PuMA performance. A fuse and switch are used for safety and control. A 5 V microcontroller, which is controlled by a computer via a USB Type B, is used to toggle the solid state relay at the appropriate duty cycle. The amplitude of the pulse is controlled by supplying the appropriate Vdc value at the voltage supply. A solid state relay is needed to produce a square wave and to avoid the transient responses from a physical

connection with quick switching times. A flyback diode is needed to eliminate sudden voltage spikes resulting from the inductive load.

3.2.2 Physical

Figure 4. The physical setup of the "fuel" reservoir, pump, vent, and disposal bottle.

Figure 4 shows the reservoir connected to the sump and pump, which drains to a disposal bottle beneath an air vent. The electrical board is set up to the right of this figure. Air venting was recommended by Environmental Health, Safety and Risk Management. All joints are properly sealed and are consistently checked for leaks. The reservoir only holds fluid during testing periods and no fluid is held in the sump or reservoir long term. The CTs were either clamped or inserted on the positive wire leading to the solenoid pump, which corresponds to the red wire in Figure 4 and the red wire connected on the bottom left of the flyback diode in Figure 3.

3.3 Procedure

All required personal protective equipment (PPE), including safety glasses and latex gloves, were used during testing. The following procedure was used to test the CTs:

1. The fuel line and sump were primed by adding damping fluid to the reservoir and pressing the red float release button twice to initiate priming of the sump.
2. Immediately after priming, a CT was attached to the red wire, either by inserting the wire like in Figure 1 or clamping the wire.
3. The leads of the CT were then attached to a breadboard, and a burden resistor was used to electrically connect the leads of the CT. The appropriate size of the burden was iteratively determined for each CT. The first burden used was 500 Ω , then was sized up depending on the response described below.
4. A two probe oscilloscope was then attached to the leads of the burden and to the leads of the pump.
5. The microcontroller was then programmed to emulate the high, medium, or low heating settings of a vented fuel oil heater. The microcontroller will not start until commanded by the computer and will send 10,000 pulses to the fuel pump.
6. The DC power supply was then turned on, and using voltage control mode, the voltage was set to 150 Vdc.

7. The electrical panel switch was then energized.
8. The program was started by sending a '1' character to the serial input of the microcontroller.
9. The oscilloscope screen was adjusted to display the voltage across the burden and across the pump at the same time and with appropriate scaling.
10. If the response of the CT was inadequate, then all powered electronics were de-energized, burden was replaced with either a higher or lower value, and then steps 4 onward were repeated.
11. All steps were repeated for each CT, since each CT had a different magnitude of burden and responded differently to the pulse.

The PuMA currently detects pump cycles with a rising voltage curve [1]. Thus, it is important for the response of the CT to match that. Preservation of the square waveform was not considered important. The main consideration was that the response of the CT had one clearly rising and one clearly falling waveform. Another characteristic considered was how much the transformer "rebounded" into the negative because this can damage the microcontroller if the magnitude is large enough. An ideal response would start at 0 V, rise then fall back to 0 V, with the response width approximating the pulse width sent to the fuel pump.

4 Results

The results are shown in the figures below, with the best burden value that produces the most ideal response also described. The burden values were iteratively chosen based on the criteria previously mentioned.

Figure 5. The response of the CR8410 had two peaks regardless of the burden used. Using a 1 k Ω burden was found to have the least objectionable response. Peak of the response is 0.4 V.

Figure 6. The response of the CT-06-05 with a 1 k Ω burden was closer to ideal, but the CT's aperture was too small for the leads, and the protective casing was damaged upon removal of the CT. Peak of the response is 0.8 V.

Figure 7. The response of the AZ 0500 with a 2.7 kΩ burden. Its response is excessively noisy, as it is not designed for measuring small currents. Peak of the response is 0.6 V.

Figure 8. The response of the CR3110 with a 10 kΩ burden has somewhat of an ideal response. It is also nowhere near its 15 V_{RMS} rated voltage [7]. Peak of the response is 0.3 V.

5 Conclusions

The results of this testing show that it is possible to use current transformers to monitor pulsed low current signals, even if the CT models used are not designed to do so, as long as preservation of the signal is not important. The burden and model of the CT is non-trivial, as shown with the comparison of the CT-06-05 and the AZ 0500. Both are similarly sized CTs and have the same turns ratio, but the responses and signal-to-noise ratios are very different. Because of the ideal response of the CT-06-05 and its discontinuation by the manufacturer, it was hoped that the AZ 0500 would behave similarly.

The recommendation drawn from the results of these tests is to move forward using the CR3110-3000 as the most likely candidate as a replacement for the MR sensor for the PuMA. Next steps include designing an amplifier to bring the signal to the appropriate voltage, noise filtering, and voltage conditioning for proper compatibility for the PuMA sensor inputs.

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